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ANALYSIS OF MODERN DRYING METHODS AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN INDUSTRY OF ILDISMEVALI PRODUCTS

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Objective. Beets are common in the Mediterranean, in Asia, India, France, Great Britain and the Scandinavian countries. Currently, there are 16 types. The purpose of drying vegetables is that by evaporating them moisture, microorganisms cannot develop and various biological processes do not occur to standard requirements.

Methods. When we process and dry the technology of drying red beets from Root products in a tape method in a convective drying device with ascorbic acid and citric acid for 10 minutes, we can initially prepare a solution by adding 20 gr of ascorbic acid to 250 ml of water and process it by soaking the beets for 10 minutes and then drying. The main purpose of processing sugar beets with citric acid is to create a technology for preserving its shape, color, vitamin and mineral substances in the composition.

Results. An increase in the level of organoleptic indicators (shape, size, taste, color and smell) is achieved when we dry beets in a convective drying device for 1 hour at a temperature of 100°C on tape 1, at a temperature of 90°C on tape 2, during the drying period for 30 minutes.

Conclusion. it is worth noting that for the experiment, sugar beet fruits are selected from the tubers, high efficiency is achieved by accelerating the drying time and drying using vacuum-sublimation methods using dielectric microwaves, reducing the drying period.

Keywords: critical moisture, bioflavanoids, drying, moisture, red beets, ascorbic acid, citric acid, convective drying, organoleptic indicator.

Introduction. The purpose of drying vegetables is to prevent them from getting wet and microorganisms cannot develop and various biological processes do not occur to a standard state. Dried fruits and vegetables are always in great demand among the population. The purpose of drying beets is to preserve the biologically active substances, organoleptic properties of the product and is used in the production of multifunctional products in various industries. Microorganisms cannot develop if the moisture content decreases from standard critical humidity indicators. This figure is 30% for bacteria and 15-20% for yeast bacteria. After drying, vegetables can be kept of good quality in the long term if their moisture content is 10-15%.

Beets-distributed in the Mediterranean, in Asia, India, France, Great Britain and the Scandinavian countries. Currently, there are 16 types.

Beets contain 86% of dry matter, protein 7.36%, carbohydrate 54.32%, calories 252.9 k per 100gr of product. makes up bald. On tape 1, 90-95°C is dried at a speed of 25-30 m/s on tape 2, and on tape 65-70°C at a speed of 50-60 m/s. Dried vegetables are well stored for a long time in special containers, at low temperatures (at 0-10°C) and when the air humidity is 60-65%. When we put dried beets in hot water, it has the peculiarity of returning to its original state. Red beets are widely used in folk medicine. It energizes the body, improves digestion and metabolism. Beets are also high in vitamin C, copper and phosphorus. It fights toxins in the body. Vitamin A is found in the leaves of Ildizmeva. The vitamin B9 it contains prevents heart disease. Stimulates the

production of hemoglobin and has a good effect in the treatment of diseases such as anemia, leukemia. This product has rejuvenating properties due to its high content of folic acid. Folic helps to form new cells.

Sugar is grown from beets to obtain sugar and feed for livestock hay, which is a necessary technical crop. Ildizmeva has an average of 17-20% sugar content. Modern sugar beet is a type of plant created entirely by scientists at the cost of achievements in the field of selection. It was created about 250 years ago as a source of sugar in Europe. The sugar beet then competes with sugar and sugarcane.

It is produced in different ways, since the microflora of vegetable juices is similar to the microflora of fleshy and meatless fruit juices. But since the juices of vegetables have a relative rarity, they are not stored long and spoil quickly. In order to ensure their long storage, it is necessary to provide heat treatment, souring with the addition of fruit juices, and to give strict attention to the sanitary conditions of enterprises to the preparation of citric or ascorbic acids. As a result of their violation, microbiological disorders of juices are observed.

Beets contain a huge amount of vitamins and minerals for the body of adults and children. Beet juice depends on the substances that make up useful and harmful products. Water is 86.5%, protein 15, mono and disaccharides 9%, starch 0.1, fiber 0.9%, organic acids 0.15%, ash 1%. The juice contains the following useful substances. iron contains folic acid, iodine, magnesium, potassium, chlorine, phosphorus, sulfur, vitamin A, organic acids, nicotinic acid, Group B vitamins, vitamin E, beta carotene, etc. The juice of

root vegetables helps to reduce bad cholesterol in the blood. This has a positive effect on the state of blood vessels. Medicinal properties of beet juice are also used in the treatment of various diseases. For example sore throat, pancreatitis, anemia, high blood pressure, runny nose, liver problems. In addition, the juice of this vegetable has an anti-cancer effect, with its regular consumption, the development of Oncology can be stopped at a very early stage. This drink works with human endurance and physical cocktail, which helps young men. This vitamin drink is more recommended for pregnant women. Reduces the risk of developing rickets in the fetus, normalizes the liver and kidneys, relieves blood pressure, helps in weight regulation. Freshly squeezed beet juice is a heavy and dangerous food for a child, since the unorganized digestive system will not yet be fully formed. The beneficial and

harmful properties of beet juice have long been known to mankind, it is used for many chronic diseases.

Methods. When we process and dry red beets from Root products with ascorbic acid for 10 minutes, we first prepare a solution by adding 20 g of ascorbic acid to 250 water and process by soaking the beets for 10 minutes and then drying them for 30 minutes at 95°C on tape 1, 100°C on tape 2 for 1 hour. The main purpose of treatment of beets with ascorbic acid is to preserve its shape, color, vitamin and mineral substances in the composition. Dried beets are rich in vitamins and minerals such as: vitamin B2 -11.1%, vitamin C -11.1%, potassium -69.1%, calcium—22.2% magnesium -33%, phosphorus -32.3%, iron -44.4%. Its cells can also withstand high temperatures due to their dense location.

Figure 1. Sugar beet product samples

Results. It is widely used in the following industries, depending on Application Industry and consumer.

Food industry (production of confectionery products, sugar production,

preparation of juice drinks, obtaining dissertation-colored and alcohol drinks, preparation of food additives, enrichment of the composition of Barberry products and production of tea drinks).

Figura-2. Examples of products from dried sugar beets.

- Pharmaceutical industry (preparation of products with medicinal concentration, Powder, Granular and syrup)
- Medicine (provides energy to the body in the production of products that have the property of increasing blood pressure and blood in the human body, accelerates digestion and metabolism.)
- Construction industry (production of cheap products with different colors, cost as natural paint products)
- Textile industry (use of fiber and synthetic materials and finished garment materials in maintaining color characteristics)
- In animal husbandry (production of double waste and hull of products with nutritional supplement and a wide range of products)

Discussion. When we dry this product, the moisture it contains is released in a certain amount and we can store it for a long time. Slight changes in color, shape and size are observed. Storage and transportation are also slightly cheaper, less space is required. When we put dried products in hot water of 60-70°C, the product acquires the property of restoring its condition by up to 90%. The main feature of sugar beet is the color. If we compare beets treated with citric acid and dried in a convective drying device in a simple way basically a sample of a product

dried with more citric acid retains itself more quality indicators and organoleptic properties, not losing much of its composition either.

In the above research device, a high level of efficiency was achieved when drying strawberry sugar beets in laboratory conditions. The duration of the drying period of products leads to the loss of 5-6% of useful elements when dried by exposure to infrared rays in a vacuum-summation method. When drying using dielectric microwaves in a new ergiyatejamkor vacuum-sublimation drying device, it was found that the useful elements contained in it were preserved in the amount of 98-99%. In the case after drying the products from their natural state, it was found that the appearance of the samples of the products is reduced in shape and size by 0.1-0.2 mm.

We studied the effect of dielectric microwaves on the cell part of the products in the fruit drying chamber using convective, dielectric microwaves. With this method, intensive heating is provided in the entire volume of the product. The difference in the effect on the temperature of the dielectric microwaves on the inside of the cell in the product accelerates the movement of moisture to the surface during the drying process.

Figure 3. Drying of sugar beets using microwaves in a vacuum-sublimation drying device research device

1. microwave drying chamber, 2. optical fiber temperature sensor, 3. vacuum valve for microwave freeze-dried products, 4. Product pad, 5. product sample, 6,7. dielectric microwave, 8. pressure nozzle, 9. vacuum valve, 10. freezing chamber, 11. management system, 12. vacuum pump, 13. closing valve, 14. cooling compressor.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it is worth noting that we selected sugar beet fruits from the fruits for the experiment, accelerating the duration of drying consists in creating a technology for obtaining waste-free products, the production of primary and secondary products.

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